

For Some Applications of Open and Closed Sets in Euclidean Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper we define some new notions open and closed sets in Euclidean spaces and remember that it has applications in areas like analysis and topology. They are fundamental to defining properties of functions and spaces, such as a function being continuous on an open set or a set being compact if it is closed and bounded. Then we state some definitions and theorems about these notions. Finally we bring some illustrative examples.

Keywords:

Euclidean Spaces Open Sets Neighborhoods manifolds An isolated point the Interior Boundary Exterior Points

Introduction:

Euclidean space is the fundamental space of geometry intended to represent physical space. First of all in Euclid's Elements which are called Euclidean n -spaces when one wants to specify their dimension. For n equal to one or two they are commonly called respectively Euclidean lines and Euclidean planes it was the three-dimensional space of Euclidean geometry but in modern mathematics there are Euclidean spaces of any positive integer dimension n [5]. The qualifier "Euclidean" is used to distinguish Euclidean spaces from other spaces that were later considered in physics and modern mathematics [4].

In mathematics an open set is a generalization of an open interval in the real line and the open sets are vitally important in topology and the Euclidean Space in geometry a two - or three-dimensional space in which the axioms and postulates of Euclidean geometry apply; also a space in any finite number of dimensions in which points are designated by coordinates (one for each dimension) and the distance between two points is given by a distance formula. Recall that an open ball is an open set. There are other subsets that every metric

space contains. In a metric space (a set along with a distance defined between any two points) along with every point P contains all points that are sufficiently near to P (that is all points whose distance to P is less than some value depending on P).

But a closed set is a set whose complement is an open set. In a topological space a closed set can be defined as a set which contains all its limit points. In a complete metric space a closed set is a set which is closed under the limit operation.

1. Structures on Euclidean space:

Definition1.1 A Euclidean Structure in a real vector space is endowed by an inner product which is symmetric bilinear form with the additional property that $\langle x, x \rangle \geq 0$ with equality if and only if $x = 0$.

Definition1.2: Let X be any n -dimensional Euclidean space (vector space over R):

1) Given $x \in X$ we define the length of x denoted $\|x\|$ to be the distance from x to 0 . By the Pythagorean theorem (In mathematics the Pythagorean theorem is a fundamental relation in Euclidean geometry between the three sides of a right triangle is equal to the sum of the areas of the squares on the other two sides) we have:

$$\|x\| = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2} \quad \text{for } x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

2) Given $x, y \in X$ we define the inner (or dot) product of x and y as:

$$\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i \quad (i = 1, \dots, n).$$

(There for the Euclidean Space is a real space with an interior product).

For example: We consider Euclidean space R^n endowed with the standard inner product:

$$\langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \cdot \langle y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n \rangle = x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2 + \dots + x_n y_n.$$

This Euclidean space is denoted by E^n .

Note :The fact that all Euclidean spaces are metric spaces while not all metric spaces are Euclidean spaces [10].

2. Open Sets in Euclidean Spaces:

Definition2.1: A subset U of the Euclidean n -space R^n is open if for every point x in U there exists a positive real number ε (depending on x) such that any point in R^n whose Euclidean distance from x is smaller than ε belongs to U . Equivalently a subset U of R^n is open if every point in U is the center of an open ball contained in U .

Definition2.2: A subset V of R^n is said to be an open set in R^n if given any point p of V there exists some strictly positive real number δ such that $B(p, \delta) \subset V$ where $B(p, \delta)$ is the open ball in R^n of radius δ about the point p defined so that:

$$\text{for } \delta > 0. B(p, \delta) = \{ x \in R^n : |x - p| < \delta \}$$

Definition2.3: Given a point p of R^n and a non-negative real number r the open ball $B(p, r)$ in R^n of radius r about p is defined to be the subset of R^n defined so that:

$$B(p, r) = \{ x \in R^n : |x - p| < r \}.$$

(Thus $B(p, r)$ is the set consisting of all points of R^n that lie within a sphere of radius r centered on the point p).

The open ball $B(p, r)$ of radius r about a point p of R^n is bounded by the sphere of radius r about p . This sphere is the set:

$$\{ x \in R^n : |x - p| = r \}.$$

Example: Let $V = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : x^2 + y^2 + z^2 < 25\}$. Then let the subset M of R^n is the open ball of radius 5 in R^n centered on the origin point $(0,0,0)$. This open ball is an open set.

Actually let p be a point of M then:

$$-5 < p < 5.$$

Let $r = 5 - |p|$. Then $r > 0$.

Moreover if x is a point of R^n that satisfies $|x - p| < r$ then:

$$|x| = |p + (x - p)| \leq |p| + |x - p| < |p| + r = 5$$

and therefore $x \in M$. Then M is an open set.

Generally an open ball of any positive radius centered on any point of a Euclidean space R^n of any dimension n is an open set in that Euclidean space.

2.1 Open Sets in Subsets of Euclidean Spaces :

Definition 2.1.1 : Let X be a subset of R^n given a point p of X and a non-negative real number r the open ball $B_x(p, r)$ in X of radius r about p is defined to be the subset of X so that:

$$B_x(p, r) = \{x \in X : |x - p| < r\}.$$

(Thus $B_x(p, r)$ is the subset consisting of all points of X that lie within a sphere of radius r centered on the point p).

Definition 2.1.2: Let X be a subset of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n . Given a point p of X and a positive real number η the open ball $B_x(p, \eta)$ in X of radius η centred on the point p consists of all points of the set X whose Euclidean distance from the point p is less than η .

We see that:

$$B_x(p, \eta) = \{x \in X : |x - p| < \eta\}$$

for all points p of X and positive real numbers η .

Example: Let A be an open set in R^n . Then for any subset X of R^n the intersection $A \cap X$ is open in X . (This follows directly from the definitions). Thus for example let S^2 be the unit sphere in R^3 given by:

$$S^2 = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1\}$$

and let N be the subset of S^2 given by:

$$N = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1 \text{ and } z > 0\}.$$

Then N is open in S^2 since $N = H \cap S^2$ where H is the open set in R^3 given by:

$$H = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z > 0\}.$$

Corollary:

1- That N is not itself an open set in R^3 . Indeed the point $(0, 0, 1)$ belongs to N but for any $\delta > 0$ the open ball (in R^3) of radius δ about $(0, 0, 1)$ contains points

(x, y, z) for which $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \neq 1$. Thus the open ball of radius δ about the point $(0, 0, 1)$ is not a subset of N .

2- Euclidean Neighborhoods point out to a set of points that are contained within a certain distance from a given point in Euclidean space.

3- In topology open sets are defined as sets that contain all of their limit points and Euclidean Neighborhoods are always open sets because they contain all of their points within a certain distance. This is known as the "open ball" property[3].

4-Euclidean-Neighborhoods are always open set.

Definition 2.1.3. A set $A \subset R^n$ is open if for each $a \in X$ there is an open ball B centered at a such that $B \subset X$.

Example: A subset of R that is not open in the closed interval $[0, 1]$ since neither $0 - \varepsilon$ nor $1 - \varepsilon$ belongs to $[0, 1]$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$. Similarly closed intervals are examples of closed sets in R .

Example: Not every subset of R^n is open or closed. There are a lot of subsets which are neither $0 + \varepsilon$ nor $1 - \varepsilon$ (open nor closed). For example the interval $(0, 1]$ in R ; the product of an open and a closed interval in R^2 .

Theorem 2.1.4: Let X be a subset of R^n . The collection of open sets in X has the following properties:

- 1- The empty set \emptyset and the whole set X are both open in X .
- 2- The union of any collection of open sets in X is itself open in X .
- 3- The intersection of any finite collection of open sets in X is itself open in X .

Proof.

1-The empty set \emptyset (Null Set) is an open set by convention. Moreover the definition of an open set is satisfied trivially by the whole set X (the empty set and X are complements of each other).

2- Let \mathcal{A} be any collection (distinct objects) of open sets in X and let W indicate the union of all the open sets belong to the family \mathcal{A} . We must show that W is itself open in X .

Let $p \in W$ then $p \in V$ for some set V belonging to the collection \mathcal{A} . It follows that there exists $\delta > 0$ such that:

$$B_x(p, \delta) \subset V. \text{ But } V \subset W \text{ and thus } B_x(p, \delta) \subset W.$$

This shows that W is open in X .

3- Let V_1, V_2, \dots, V_K be a finite collection of subsets of X that are open in X and let $V \in V_1 \cap V_2 \dots \cap V_K$ of these sets. And let $p \in V$.

Now $p \in V_{j+1}$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$ and therefore there exist strictly positive real-numbers $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_K$ such that:

$$B_x(p, \delta_{j+1}) \subset V_{j+1} \text{ for } j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1.$$

Let δ be the minimum of $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_K$. Then $\delta > 0$. (This is where we need the fact that we are dealing with a finite collection of sets).

Then $B_x(p, \delta) \subset B_x(p, \delta_{j+1}) \subset V_{j+1}$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$,

and thus :

$$B_x(p, \delta) \subset V.$$

Thus the intersection V of the sets $V_1 \cap V_2 \dots \cap V_K$ is itself open in X .

Corollary:

The closure of a set A is the intersection of all closed sets containing A .

Example: For each $k > 0$ let $V_k = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : k^2(x^2 + y^2 + z^2) < 1\}$. Now each set V_k is an open ball of radius $1/k$ about the origin and is therefore an open set in R^3 .

But the intersection of the sets V_k for all positive integers k is the set $\{(0, 0, 0)\}$ and thus the intersection of the sets V_k for all positive integers k is not itself an open set in R^3 .

This example explain that infinite intersections of open sets need not be open.

Example : Let A_n be the open intervals $(-1/n, 1/n)$ in R . Then A_n

are open sets but the intersection $T = \bigcap_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n = \{0\}$ is not open.

Lemma 2.1.5 : A set is open if and only if it is equal to the union of a collection of open balls.

Proof.

According to Theorem 2.1.4 (2) the union of any collection of open balls is open.

On the other hand if A is open then for every point $x \in A$ there

exists a ball $B(x)$ about x lying in A . We have $A = \bigcup_{x \in A} B(x)$. Indeed the union $\bigcup_{x \in A} B(x)$ is a subset of A because every ball $B(x)$ is a subset of A and since $x \in B(x)$ the union contains every point $x \in A$.

3. Closed Sets in Euclidean Spaces:

Definition 3.1: Let X be a subset of R^n . A subset F of X is said to be closed in X if and only if its complement $X \setminus F$ in X is open in X .

(Recall that $X \setminus F = \{x \in X : x \notin F\}$).

Example: The closed interval $[a, b]$ of real numbers is closed.

Theorem 3.2: Let X be a subset of R^n . The collection of closed sets in X has the following properties:

- 1-The empty set \emptyset and the whole set X are both closed in X .
- 2- The intersection of any collection of closed sets in X is itself closed in X .
- 3- The union of any finite collection of closed sets in X is itself closed in X .

Proof.

1-The empty set \emptyset is closed set by convention. Moreover the definition of set is closed satisfied trivially by the whole set X .

2-Let \mathcal{A} be any collection of closed sets in X and let W indicate the union of all the closed sets belong to the family \mathcal{A} . We must show that W is itself closed in X .

Let $p \in W$ then $p \in V$ for some set V belonging to the collection \mathcal{A} . It follows that there exists $\delta > 0$ such that:

$$V \subset W \text{ and thus } B_x(p, \delta) \subset W \cdot B_x(p, \delta) \subset V$$

This shows that W is closed in X .

3- Let V_1, V_2, \dots, V_K be a finite collection of subsets of X that are closed open in X and let $V \in V_1 \cap V_2 \dots \cap V_K$ of these sets. And let $p \in V$.

Now $p \in V_{j+1}$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$ and therefore there exist strictly

positive real numbers $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_K$ such that:

$$B_x(p, \delta_{j+1}) \subset V_{j+1} \text{ for } j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1.$$

Let δ be the minimum of $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_K$. Then $\delta > 0$. (This is where we need the fact that we are dealing with a finite collection of sets).

Then $B_x(p, \delta) \subset B_x(p, \delta_{j+1}) \subset V_{j+1}$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$,

and thus :

$$B_x(p, \delta) \subset V.$$

Thus the intersection V of the sets $V_1 \cap V_2, \dots, \cap V_K$ is itself closed in X .

Example : The sets

$$\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z \geq c\}$$

$$\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z \leq c\} \text{ and}$$

$$\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z = c\}$$

are closed sets in R^n for each real number c since the complements of these sets are open in R^3 .

Example: Let X be a subset of R^n and let x_0 be a point of X . Then the sets

$$\{x \in X : |x - x_0| \leq r\} \text{ and}$$

$$\{x \in X : |x - x_0| \geq r\}$$

are closed for each non-negative real number r . In particular the set $\{x_0\}$ consisting of the single point x_0 is a closed set.

For **Example** if is defined to be the interior of a half cone intersected by any plane that does not pass through the vertex of the cone then is an open set.

Definition 3.3: A set $S \subseteq R_n$ is said to be Open if S is precisely the set of all of its interior points i.e. $S = \text{int}(S)$

Definition 3.4: A set $S \subseteq R_n$ is said to be Closed if S_c is open.

Recall from the Interior Boundary and Exterior Points in Euclidean Space that if $S \subseteq R_n$ then a point $a \in R_n$ is said to be an interior point of S if there exists an $r > 0$ such that $B(a, r) \subseteq S$.

Furthermore a is said to be a boundary point of S if for every $r > 0$ we have that there exists $xy \in B(a, r)$ such that $x \in S$ and $y \in S_c$. We also said that a point a is called an exterior point of S if $a \in S_c \setminus \text{bdry}(S)$.

We are now ready to formally define the concept of an open and closed set.

Example: Let $H = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z > c\}$ where c is some real number. Then H is an open set in R^3 . Indeed let p be a point of H .

Then $p = (u, v, w)$ where $w > c$.

Let $\delta = w - c$. If the distance from a point (x, y, z) to the point (u, v, w) is less than δ then $|z - w| < \delta$ and hence $z > c$ so that $(x, y, z) \in H$.

Thus $B(p, \delta) \subset H$ and therefore H is an open set. The previous example can be generalized.

Given any integer $i = 1, \dots, n$ and given any real number c_i the sets $\{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in R^n : x_i > c_i\}$ and $\{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in R^n : x_i < c_i\}$ are open sets in R^n .

A subset V of X is said to be open in X if given any point of there exists an open ball in X of positive radius centred on that point which is wholly contained within the set V .

By convention the empty set \emptyset is also considered to be open in the given set X (on the grounds that there does not exist any point of the empty set that is not the centre of some open ball contained in the empty set).

Thus given any subset X of R^n and given any subset V of X the set V is said to be open in X if and only if given any point p of V there exists some strictly positive real number δ such that $B_x(p, \delta) \subset V$ where:

$$B_x(p, \delta) = \{x \in X : |x - p| < \delta\}$$

Example : Let V be an open set in R^n . Then for any subset X of R^n the intersection $V \cap X$ is open in X . (This follows directly from the definitions.)

Definition 3.5 [7]: A subset O of a metric space X (a metric space is a set together with a notion of distance between its elements usually called points) is an open set if O is a neighborhood of each of its points.

Indeed the point $(0, 0, 1)$ belongs to N but for any positive real number δ the open ball (in R^n) of radius δ centred on $(0, 0, 1)$ contains points (x, y, z) for which $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1$. Thus the open ball of radius δ centred on the point $(0, 0, 1)$ is not a subset of N .

Lemma 3.6: Let X be a subset of R^n and let p be a point of X . Then for any positive real number η the open ball $B_x(p, \eta)$ in X of radius η centred on p is open in X .

Proof.

Let q be an element of $B_x(p, \eta)$. We must show that there exists some positive real number δ such that:

$$B_x(p, \delta) \subset B_x(p, \eta)$$

Let $\delta = \eta - |q - p|$. Then $\delta > 0$ since $|q - p| < \eta$.

Moreover if $x \in B_x(p, \delta)$ then $|x - p| \leq |x - q| + |q - p| < \delta + |q - p| = \eta$ by the Triangle Inequality and hence:

$$x \in B_x(p, \eta). \text{ Thus } B_x(p, \delta) \subset B_x(p, \eta)$$

This shows that $B_x(p, \eta)$ is an open set as required.

Lemma 3.7[7]: Let X be a subset of R^n and let p be a point of X . Then for any non-negative real number η the set $\{x \in X : |x - p| > \eta\}$ is an open set in X .

Proof.

Let q be a point of X satisfying $|q - p| > \eta$ and let x be any point of X satisfying $|x - q| < \delta$,

where $\delta = |q - p| - \eta$.

Then $|q - p| \leq |q - x| + |x - p|$ by the Triangle Inequality and therefore $|x - p| \geq |q - p| - |x - q| > |q - p| - \delta = \eta$.

Thus $B_x(q, \delta)$ is contained in the given set. The result follows.

Example : The set $\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : x^2 + y^2 + z^2 < 4 \text{ and } z > 1\}$

is an open set in R^3 since it is the intersection of the open ball of radius 2 centred on the origin with the open set $\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z > 1\}$.

Example: The set $\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : x^2 + y^2 + z^2 < 4 \text{ or } z > 1\}$ is an open set in R^3 since it is the union of the open ball of radius 2 centred on the origin with the open set $\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : z > 1\}$.

Example: The set $\{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : (x - n)^2 + y^2 + z^2 < 4 \text{ for some } n \in Z\}$ is an open set in R^3 since it is the union of the open balls of radius 2 centred on the points $(n, 0, 0)$ for all integers n .

Example: For each positive integer k let $V_k = \{(x, y, z) \in R^3 : k^2 (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) < 1\}$.

Now each set V_k is an open ball of radius $1/k$ centred on the origin and is therefore an open set in R^3 .

However the intersection of the sets V_k for all positive integers k is the set $\{(0, 0, 0)\}$

and thus the intersection of the sets V_k for all positive integers k is not itself an open set in R .

This example demonstrates that infinite intersections of open sets need not be open.

Proposition 3.8: Let X be a subset of R^n and let W be a subset of X . Then W is open in X if and only if there exists some open set V in R^n for which $W = V \cap X$.

Proof .

First suppose that $W = V \cap X$ for some open set V in R^n . Let $p \in W$. Then the definition of open sets in R^n ensures that there exists some positive real number δ such that :

$$\{x \in R^n : |x - p| < \delta\} \subset V. \text{ Then } \{x \in X : |x - p| < \delta\} \subset W.$$

This shows that W is open in X .

Conversely suppose that the subset W of X is open in X . For each point p of W there exists some positive real number δ_p such that :

$$\{x \in X : |x - p| < \delta_p\} \subset W.$$

For each $p \in W$ let $B(p, \delta_p)$ denote the open ball in R^n of radius δ_p centred on the point p so that:

$$B(p, \delta_p) = \{x \in R^n : |x - p| < \delta_p\}$$

for all $p \in W$ and let V be the union of all the open balls $B(p, \delta_p)$ as p ranges over all the points of W .

Then V is an open set in R^n . Indeed every open ball in R^n is an open set (Lemma 3.7) and any union of open sets in R^n is itself an open set (Proposition 3.8). The set V is a union of open balls.

It is therefore a union of open sets and so must itself be an open set. Now

$$B(p, \delta_p) \cap X \subset W \quad \text{for all } p \in W.$$

Also every point of V belongs to $B(p, \delta_p)$ for at least one point p of W .

It follows that $V \cap X \subset W$. But $p \in B(p, \delta_p)$ and $B(p, \delta_p) \subset V$ for all $p \in W$ and therefore $W \subset V$ and thus $W \subset V \cap X$. It follows that $W = V \cap X$.

4. Limit Points of Subsets (open or close)of Euclidean Spaces

Definition 4.1: Let X be a subset of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n and let $p \in R^n$. The point p is said to be a limit point of the set X if given any positive real number δ there exists some point x of X for which $0 < |x - p| < \delta$.

Lemma 4.2: Let X be a subset of n – dimensional Euclidean space R^n and let $p \in R^n$. Then the point p is a limit point of the set X if and only if there exists

an infinite sequence x_1, x_2, \dots of points of X all distinct from the point p such that $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} x_j = p$.

Proof.

Suppose that p is a limit point of X . Then for each positive integer j there exists a point x_j of X for which $0 < |x_j - p| < 1/j$. The points x_j satisfying this condition then constitute an infinite sequence x_1, x_2, \dots of points of X all distinct from the point p that converge to the point p .

Conversely suppose that p is some point of R^n that is the limit of some infinite sequence x_1, x_2, \dots of points of X that are all distinct from the point p . Let $\delta > 0$ be given. The definition of convergence ensures that there exists a positive integer N such that $|x_j - p| < \delta$ whenever $j \geq N$. Moreover $|x_j - p| > 0$ for all positive integers j .

Thus $0 < |x_j - p| < \delta$ when the positive integer j is sufficiently large. Thus the point p is a limit point of the set X as required.

Definition 4.3: Let X be a subset of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n . A point p of X is said to be an isolated point of X if it is not a limit point of X .

Let X be a subset of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n and let $p \in X$. It follows immediately from the definition of isolated points that the point p is an isolated point of the set X if and only if there exists some strictly positive real number δ for which:

$$\{x \in X : |x - p| < \delta\} = \{p\}.$$

Lemma 4.4: A subset F of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n is closed in R^n if and only if it contains its limit points

Proof.

Let F be a closed set in R^n and let p be a limit point of F . There exists an infinite sequence of points of F that converges to the point p then $p \in F$.

Thus if the set F is closed then it contains its limit points.

Conversely let F be a subset of R^n that contains its limit points. Let $p \in R^n \setminus F$. Then p is not a limit point of F . It follows from the definition of limit points that there exists some positive real number δ for which

$$\{x \in F : 0 < |x - p| < \delta\} = \emptyset.$$

It then follows from this that the open ball in R^n of radius δ about the point p is contained in the complement of F . We conclude therefore that the complement of F in R^n is open in R^n and thus F is closed in R^n .

Lemma 4.5[4]: A subset F of n -dimensional Euclidean space R^n is closed in R^n if and only if it contains its limit points.

Proof.

Let F be a closed set in R^n and let p be a limit point of F . It follows from Lemma (4.2) that there exists an infinite sequence of points of F that converges to the point p and that $p \in F$. Thus if the set F is closed then it contains its limit points.

Corollaries :

1-Since Euclidean space with the Euclidean distance is a metric space A subset U of a metric space (M, d) is called *open* if for any point x in U there exists

a real number $\varepsilon > 0$ such that any point y satisfying $d(x, y) < \varepsilon$ belongs to U . Equivalently U is open if every point in U has a neighborhood contained in U

2-The concept is required to define and make sense of topological space and other topological structures that deal with the notions of closeness and convergence for spaces such as metric spaces and uniform spaces.

3-A set might be open closed both or neither. In particular open and closed sets are not mutually exclusive meaning that it is in general possible for a subset of a topological space to simultaneously be both an open subset *and* a closed subset. Such subsets are known as *close*.

5.Conclusion:

In this paper we use some applications of Open and Closed Sets in Euclidean Spaces of any positive integer dimension- n firstly the structures on Euclidean space and the limit Points of subsets (open or closed sets) with some definitions theories and examples .

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